

Threatened *Rhododendron* species at the Bergen University Gardens

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Botanic gardens and the conservation of biological diversity

Human impact on the natural environment, particularly through changing land use, the introduction of invasive alien species, and climate change, is resulting in increasing threats to biodiversity worldwide (Díaz & al., 2019). Many plant species are threatened with extinction in the wild. Those that are naturally rare or have narrow distributions are particularly vulnerable, as are those found in habitats disproportionately impacted by human exploitation (such as land suitable for agriculture or development) or shifting climates (such as coastal or mountain alpine zones).

The most important way to protect the ongoing existence of these species is to preserve the habitats in which they grow naturally, including their complex web of co-dependent organisms such as pollinators, herbivores, and their predators. Such 'in situ' conservation will not always be possible. Botanic gardens offer a last chance to preserve biological diversity that will otherwise become extinct. In contrast to 'in situ' conservation, these and other living collections, such as zoos or seed banks, that preserve biodiversity outside its native habitat can be used for 'ex situ' conservation.

The aim of ex situ conservation is to enable future reintroductions of species in the wild. For those reintroductions to be successful in the long-term, the species need to retain their potential to adapt in a naturally fluctuating environment. This means maximising genetic diversity within species, for which we need to keep numerous individuals from different populations. The future for a single clone or questionable garden hybrid can hardly be more than a reminder of what we once had. We need a viable new start available into the indefinite future. This is a huge challenge.

Prioritizing survival of threatened species – a new initiative

Mortality is not unusual in botanic gardens. It is an inevitable consequence of attempting to grow a great many different plants, often of wild origin and from across the world. Each species or even individual is unique in its ability to thrive given different soils, temperatures, rainfall, and seasonal variability. Unlike a commercial grower specializing in a limited range of crop or cultivar clones that have been selected to perform optimally under standard conditions, we are dealing with a maximally diverse band of botanical divas.

Documenting losses in these 'horticultural experiments' can inform our understanding of the ecological tolerances of species outside their natural ranges. However, with the accelerating loss of biodiversity worldwide we must now recognise that some of our collections are too important to leave to chance. At the University Gardens we are now putting extra effort into long term conservation of threatened species.

Growing threatened Rhododendron species at the Arboretum

We currently hold seven Critically Endangered (CR) and 14 Endangered (EN) *Rhododendron* species. These are the two most severe categories of extinction threat defined by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) in their Red List of Threatened Species (<https://www.iucnredlist.org/>). We are taking steps to ensure that these species are secured, for example through vegetative propagation and protected overwintering.

We also act as a safe site for the conservation of dozens more species that have been assessed as Vulnerable (VU) or Near Threatened (NT). The IUCN categories of threat reflect the distribution range and rarity of species and the prospects for continuity of their habitats. These factors change over time – generally for the worse – and each assessment therefore has a 10-year shelf-life. Many of the assessments published in the 2011 volume by RBGE’s Gibbs, Chamberlain & Argent (Gibbs & al., 2011) now need updating. As their status is reviewed, we can expect a proportion of the species on our collections to move to the more severe categories. We are therefore acting to secure all our wild-collected threatened species accessions.

Botanic gardens work together

Botanic gardens can realistically attempt ex situ conservation only because of their relative permanence as institutions, the detailed documentation of their collections, and their special position in the modern context of the CBD (Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 2020). Botanic gardens can obtain and share plant material that must otherwise remain unavailable for commercial exploitation. Although most plant species found in the collections of a botanic garden will also be held by at least a handful of other such institutions, each garden nevertheless tends to hold unique collections. This is a matter of concern.

For species that are already extinct in the wild, the price of failure for the custodian of the last living specimen is the loss of millions of years of unique accumulated evolutionary history with all its future potential uses and intrinsic value for everyone. No garden is immune to sudden calamity, whether that is late frost, drought, infestation, or even fires that might impact entire collections. For any single botanic garden, this would be an intolerably heavy responsibility.

However, we are not alone. Thousands of botanic gardens worldwide have the potential to spread both the burden and the risk of looking after these treasures, when we work together and coordinate our efforts. Not every garden can look after everything – the numbers of species are just too high – but we are well placed to focus on our own areas of expertise. Here at the University Gardens, we have the ideal conditions, established knowledge, and collections of *Rhododendron* (Jørgensen, 1996; Salvesen & al., 2021) to contribute internationally to conservation of species. We are part of an international group of gardens coordinated at the Royal Botanic Garden, Edinburgh (RBGE) under Botanic Gardens Conservation International (BGCI)’s ‘Global Conservation Consortium for *Rhododendron*’ (<https://www.globalconservationconsortia.org/gcc/rhododendron/>).

By sharing information and material, we can aim to both back up our unique collections and better represent the genetic diversity of species in a ‘meta-collection’ spread across multiple gardens.

Threatened species at the University Gardens – more than just Rhododendron

Rhododendrons are not the only threatened species we look after. We hold collections of threatened conifers such as *Wollemia nobilis*, two threatened species of *Fraxinus* and several of *Sorbus* (Salvesen & al., 2021), as well as contributing to seed banking of rare and endangered species in Norway. We also lead a dedicated GCC for the other Ericaceae mega-genus, *Erica*, with its similar numbers of

threatened species (Pirie & al., 2022) and hold an example of *Erica verticillata*, a Cape heath that is extinct in the wild.

We hope that the visiting public will appreciate the chance to see these rarities for themselves. If you are at Milde, look out for the special signs and displays highlighting threatened species in the collections. In the future, we will work together with BGCI and our international partners to promote conservation activities in the native habitats and how we can support them.

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